

BUCKLING, FAILURE AND OPTIMIZATION OF DOUBLY-CURVED LAMINATED SHELLS - THEORETICAL FORMULATIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

Aleksander Muc
Institute of Mechanics & Machine Design
Cracow University of Technology, Kraków, Poland.

ABSTRACT

The theoretical approach presented in the paper is applied to the analysis of failure modes (bifurcation buckling, FPF and interlaminar failure) of FRP pressure vessels subjected to the external (vacuum) pressure. The developed relations are based on geometrically nonlinear, third-order transverse shear shell theory in the global-local approach. A special attention is focused on the formulation of optimization problems in this area. An extensive complementary experimental investigations was carried out to confirm the theoretical findings. The numerical results are also compared with design codes predictions.

INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that laminated composite structure present additional difficulties, in terms of a parametric, theoretical description of the structural behaviour, over and above the encountered in isotropic, material configurations. Therefore, as it can be easily noticed the present state of knowledge in this area still lag far behind that for isotropic, stiffened and sandwich shells. Usually, the design of fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) vessels utilizes equations developed for isotropic (metallic) vessels, not taking into account laminate configurations. The additional problems arise in the proper theoretical modelling of anisotropic structures enabling to describe accurate enough all possible failure modes and to predict failure loads.

In the present work we intend to look insight the problem of limit states for composite domed heads with a cylindrical portion and subjected to external pressure. The limit states of vessels are understood in the sense of different failure modes for composites, such as: bifurcation buckling, first-ply-failure (FPF) and interlaminar failure (delaminations). The results of theoretical investigations are compared with experimental results and design code predictions. Finally, by the analysis of various numerical results we arrive at the conclusion that the optimization with respect to various design variables may offer a reasonable solution in the design of FRP pressure vessels.

GOVERNING RELATIONS

In the present approach we assume that the three components of the displacement vector are expanded in power series corresponding to the third-order displacement field:

$$\begin{aligned} u_\alpha(x_1, x_2, z) &= v_\alpha(x_1, x_2) + z\phi_\alpha(x_1, x_2) + \frac{1}{2}z^2\psi_\alpha(x_1, x_2) + \frac{1}{3}z^3\theta_\alpha(x_1, x_2) \\ u_3(x_1, x_2, z) &= w(x_1, x_2) + z\psi_3(x_1, x_2) + z^2\theta_3(x_1, x_2) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

It is assumed that the Greek symbols change from 1 to 2 and the small Latin subscripts from 1 to 3. In Eqs (1) the transverse deflection is expanded only up to second order for consistency of transverse shear strains. It is obvious that from the above expressions as the special cases shell theories of the lower orders than third can be obtained, i.e. the Love-Kirchhoff theory or the first-order shear deformation theory. The theory contains more unknowns than the first-order shear deformation theory, but accounts for parabolic distributions of the transverse shear strains and linear distributions of the normal strains through the shell thickness. In addition, it takes into account geometrical nonlinearities in the sense of large deflections and moderate rotations of the normal to the shell midsurface. Thus, it predicts the deflections and stresses more accurately when compared to the first-order theory.

Using the classical form of 3-D nonlinear geometrical relations one can derive the nonlinear explicit form of geometrical 2-D relations in terms of unknown functions $u_{\alpha,w}, \phi_\alpha, \psi_i, \theta_i$ and the coordinate z , e.g. [1]. In addition, we assume also that all nonlinear terms involving $\phi_\alpha, \psi_i, \theta_i$ are neglected in writing the strains. Hence, as we represent the components of the strain tensor ε_{ij} in the following form:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ij(o)} + z\varepsilon_{ij(1)} + z^2\varepsilon_{ij(2)} + z^3\varepsilon_{ij(3)}, \quad [\varepsilon] = [\varepsilon_{ij(o)}, \varepsilon_{ij(1)}, \varepsilon_{ij(2)}, \varepsilon_{ij(3)}] \quad (2)$$

all nonlinear terms having the products of $u_{\alpha,w}$ and their derivatives are retained only in the components $\varepsilon_{ij(o)}$ in the series expansion (2). For the considered type of kinematical hypothesis given by Eqs (1) the stress resultants are defined in the following way:

$$[\mathbf{P}] = \{N_{ij}, M_{ij}, P_{ij}, R_{ij}\} = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \{1, z, z^2, z^3\} \sigma_{ij} dz \quad (3)$$

The physical 3-D relations joining stress and strain tensors are given in the classical form of generalized Hook's law (Pagano [2]):

$$[\sigma] = [Q][\varepsilon], [Q] = [T]^{(k)}[\bar{Q}]^{(k)}[T]^{(k)T} \quad (4)$$

where $[\bar{Q}]^{(k)}$ denotes the stiffness matrix of the k -th layer in the material coordinate system, and $[T]^{(k)}$ is the rotation tensor from the local coordinate system to the global one. The terms of the matrix $[T]^{(k)}$ are functions of the rotation angle β_k . In the considerations it is assumed that the material is transversely isotropic, i.e. $E_{22} = E_{33}, \nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$.

FAILURE ANALYSIS

It is known that the buckling analysis can be carried out with the use of the global approach, whereas FPF or interlaminar strength should be determined with the use of local models for laminated composites. The developed computer code [3] (the FE discretisation) permits to join two mentioned-above approaches via the global-local analysis. This approach reduces

significantly time of computations in the comparison with local models and allows to obtain correct and accurate results. The improvement is achieved by the division of the whole shell meridian into two categories of segments - Fig.1. In the first if failure occurs in the sense of the strength criteria then the laminate is divided into 2 sublaminates (their number is lower than the number of plies in the laminate). For the second type of segments the strength limits are not detected and the global analysis may be conducted up to the bifurcation failure. As the laminate is divided into sublaminates, in each of the sublaminates the set of kinematical variables given by Eqs (1), geometrical and constitutive relations are defined independently. Two different types of relations are connected by the additional set of continuity equations on the boundaries $S^{(p,r)}$. In addition, we enforce the vanishing of transverse shear stresses on the top and bottom surfaces of the laminates (1),(4) or the sublaminates (2),(3) - Fig.1. The present approach shows the decrease (by the factor 10-15 %) of failure loads in the comparison to results of the global analysis.

Using the standard finite element procedures, at a load $p=p_f + \Delta p$ the eigenvalues are calculated by means of a sequence of the problems:

$$\sum_e [K^e(p^f) + \eta K_g^e(\Delta p)] [g_e] = 0, \quad [g_e]^T = [d_e, \lambda^C, \lambda^D] \quad (5)$$

where $K^e(p^f)$, $K_g^e(\Delta p)$ and η are the generalized stiffness matrix, geometric stiffness matrix and load factor, respectively. The vector $[g_e]$ consists of the nodal variables d_e and Lagrange multipliers λ^C, λ^D .

The strength of the k th layer in the laminate (FPF) is represented via the quadratic criterion in the stress space:

$$\Psi([\bar{\sigma}^{(k)}]) = [\bar{\sigma}^{(k)}]^T [W][\bar{\sigma}^{(k)}] + [Z][\bar{\sigma}^{(k)}] \quad (6)$$

The terms in the matrices $[W], [Z]$ are evaluated experimentally, and the matrix $[W]$ is symmetric.

The strength criterion for predicting delamination initiation can be defined in the following form:

$$F_{kl} \sigma_k \sigma_l + G_k \sigma_k = 1, \quad k, l = 4, 5, 6 \quad (7)$$

where $\sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6$ are the transverse shear components $\sigma_{13}, \sigma_{23}, \sigma_{33}$, respectively. F_{kl} and G_k denote the coefficients being the functions of the interlaminar strength for the stress components σ_l . However, it should be emphasized that there is no single criterion that can predict first-ply- or interlaminar failure of composites entirely, i.e. the explicit form of the matrices $[W], [Z]$ or the coefficients F_{kl}, G_k is different for various composite materials.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The aim of the present numerical investigations is to indicate and illustrate characteristic features of composite thinwalled structure behaviour under external pressure. The used numerical code, developed by the author [3], permits to analyse axisymmetric shell structures having different kinematic boundary conditions. For FRP pressure vessels the influence of directional and anisotropic properties of composite materials on failure loads is one of the fundamental point of interest. As structural layers of vessels are composed of woven roving (WR) materials the anisotropic properties of composite materials have insignificant effects on variations of failure loads with fibre orientations. However, the results are drastically changed as unidirectional composites are employed in constructions.

In order to obtain the dimensionless form of the results failure pressures p_f are related to:

$$\Lambda = \frac{2\sqrt{E_1 E_2}}{\sqrt{3(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})}} \left(\frac{2t}{D}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

where t is a shell thickness and D denotes the diameter of the cylindrical portion of vessels (for hemispheres $D=2R$).

Figure 2 demonstrates the variations of failure pressures with fibre orientations β for angle-ply, clamped hemispherical domed heads made of unidirectional CFRP ($E_1/E_2 = 203/11.2, E_1/G_{12}=203/8.4$). The failure envelopes have been evaluated taking into account two failure criteria, i.e. bifurcation buckling - Eqn (5) and the FPF criterion - Eqn (6) in the form proposed by Tsai-Wu and the ϵ_{max} criterion. The differences between failure pressures computed with the use of the Tsai-Wu (quadratic) and the ϵ_{max} criteria are negligibly small. As the angle β is less than 45° FPF occurs and it precedes the bifurcation buckling failure mode detected in the surrounding of $\beta = 45^\circ$. If the buckling analysis is carried out only the bifurcation buckling occurs in the whole interval $[0^\circ, 45^\circ]$ but buckling pressures are much higher than those corresponding to the first-ply-failure mode. For $\beta \geq 45^\circ$ the axisymmetric collapse is a dominating failure mode. The character of the failure pressures distributions and the types of failure modes are rather independent on the R/t thickness ratio. It is worth to note the difference between the maximum (bifurcation buckling) and the minimum (FPF at the shell apex) of the failure pressures. More information about the discussed above problems can be found in Ref. [4].

The addition of the cylindrical portion having the length L to domed heads reduces significantly buckling pressures, since buckling of cylinders precedes buckling of domed heads. However, the above effect is strongly dependent on the value of the aspect ratio t^{head}/t^{cylind} - see Fig.3. Figure 3 is a comparison of buckling pressures for three types of structures: a simply supported cylinder (A), a clamped cylinder with a torispherical head ($R/D=1, r/D=0.1$) - (B) and the half of the pressure vessel (with the identical dished ends as the above) - (C). The plotted curves show the influence of the ratio t^{head}/D on buckling pressures for constructions made of unidirectional GFRP ($E_1/E_2 = 38.6/8.27, E_1/G_{12}=38.6/4.1$) having the following configuration $[45^\circ, 36^\circ, 27^\circ, 18^\circ, 9^\circ, 0^\circ]_S$.

It should be pointed out that the use of the classical or the first-order transverse shear shell theories in the application to the bifurcation buckling analysis or of the global approach in the FPF study results in the significant increase of failure pressures in the comparison to the proposed herein formulation of the problem.

Of course, design of FRP vessels subjected to external pressure can (or rather should) be carried out in the accordance with various national design codes. It is interesting to compare results of rigorous analytical approach with predictions of various codes. Bifurcation buckling of structures and first-ply-failure can be evaluated with the help of design codes, whereas the interlaminar failure (delaminations) are taken into account via safety (design) factors only.

First of all it is worth to note that different codes use different levels of the analysis to describe fracture mechanisms. For instance, the British Standard use the macroscopic approach treating the laminate as a homogeneous quantity. The ASME Regulations requirements for an acceptable design are directed into the first-ply-failure study of each individual plies in the laminate, with the help of computer based methods since hand calculations become impossible, especially as more dangerous compressive stress occurs. The macroscopic fracture analysis seems to be not accurate (overestimates failure loads) and in the future it will be entirely replaced by generally acceptable approach basing on the FPF study with the use of computer programs similarly as it is presented in this work.

According to design codes buckling analysis of FRP vessels under external pressure is carried out separately for heads and cylinders, in our opinion, due to the method of fabrication. The comparison of buckling loads calculated theoretically and with the aid of design codes for the perfect spherical shells made of WR or unidirectional GFRP and clamped at the edges is presented in Fig.4. However, the introduced safety factors F in design codes are assumed to be equal to 1. As it may be observed for WR composite materials the failure

loads predicted with the use of design codes are too conservative (due to geometric initial imperfections) but the plotted curves have the identical distributions with fibre orientations. However, the codes describe buckling pressures of spherical shells made of unidirectional composites much worse than for WR materials especially BS 4994. This is mainly caused by the assumed definitions of material properties (quasi-isotropy).

Design codes provides also the separate equations that are used to determine allowable external pressures for cylinders in FRP pressure vessels. The comparison of them with the strict numerical results leads to the same conclusion as for composite heads.

OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS

Engineers should select among several possible solutions that design which, when compared with the others can be considered as the best one, but the best with respect to some parameters dictated by economy, performance of structures, or other significant features. As it may be seen in Figs 2-4 the proper choice becomes much more difficult for composite structures, especially for those made of filament winding. In general, the optimization problems encountered in this area can be grouped into three categories: 1) design of a composite topology (layout), 2) sizing optimization and 3) shape optimization. The first group of optimization problems is directly connected with the layered structure of laminates constituting the pressure vessel wall. Thus, usually the design variables are: ply orientations of layers and the positions of each individual ply with respect to the shell midsurface. According to the theory of laminated thin-walled structures the above-mentioned design variables define completely all terms in the stiffness matrix [Q] - Eqn (4). The influence of those parameters is illustrated in Figs 2 and 4.

The designer must also select in a proper way the cross-sectional dimensions of the structural members; if this selection is made through the application of optimization techniques, then the design procedure is called sizing optimization. This means that if we are dealing with shell structures, then the objective is to find optimal thickness distributions. The importance of sizing optimization is evidently proved in Fig.3.

The third group concerns mainly shape optimization of inspection openings in vessels and may be conducted in the similar manner as for isotropic structures, e.g. [5].

For FRP pressure vessels the objective of the optimization problem can be formulated as the maximization of failure loads - failure is understood in the sense of the criteria given by Eqs (5)-(7). Therefore, the present problem belongs to the class of multicriteria optimization problems and the objective of the optimization may be written as follows:

$$\min_{s_i} [\max_j (-w_j \cdot f_j)] \tag{9}$$

It is subjected to constraint conditions, equations for variables (failure criteria - Eqs (5)-(7), $j=3$) and state equations discretized with the use of FE. w_j are given weighting factors for a separate design criterion functions f_j - Eqs (5)-(7), and s_j denotes the appropriate set of design variables. Since the min-max objective function is not differentiable with respect to the design parameters we develop a bound formulation. By this technique we introduce an additional design variable λ which is termed the bound parameter and write Eqn (9) as the differentiable problem:

$$\min_{s_i, \lambda} (-\lambda) \text{ subject to constraints : } -w_j \cdot f_j \leq -\lambda \iff \lambda \leq w_j \cdot f_j \tag{10}$$

Figure 5 is a plot of the optimal failure pressures versus the shallowness parameter ρ :

$$\rho = \sqrt[4]{12(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})} \frac{D}{2\sqrt{Rt}} \tag{11}$$

The problem deals with the analysis of 12 layered clamped spherical domed ends made of unidirectional GFRP. For the illustration of the problem the optimal failure pressures for each types of failure criteria are also drawn. The design variables are a set of fibre orientations β_k of each individual plies, whereas the thicknesses of plies are assumed to be constant and equal to $t/12$. The optimal fibre orientations are functions of the parameter ρ . For shallow shells ($\rho \leq 6$) the first-ply-failure is a dominating failure mode and the optimal orientation is 45° . However, the values of failure loads coincide almost with those corresponding to the bifurcation buckling pressure for shells made of fibres oriented at 45° and to the pressure associated with the delamination failure mode. For deeper shells the delamination failure mode is dominating, and the quasi-isotropy is an optimal fibre configuration. Let us note that the values of the optimal failure pressures corresponding to the FPF and the delamination modes are lower than the failure pressure associated with the bifurcation buckling failure mode. The optimal fibre orientation with respect to bifurcation buckling failure mode is 0° for shallow spheres and the quasi-isotropy for deep shells. The delamination failure mode is always associated with the local bifurcation buckling of the thinner sublaminates - the region (3) in Fig.1. More examples dealing with a layout optimization for doubly-curved shells is presented in Ref. [6].

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

A series of experimental tests have been conducted in order to verify the values of failure pressures evaluated with the aid of the computer code as well as failure modes. The experimental results deal with failure tests on 0.2-0.3 m diameter domes made of woven roving composite materials (carbon and glass/epoxy resin) and subjected to uniform external pressure. The vacuum bag technique was used to make the various composite shells. The moulds were obtained with the use of numerically controlled machine to avoid initial shape imperfections. Each of moulds corresponded to the geometrical ratios of heads enumerated in Table 1. The measured volume fraction of fibres was about 50%. Shells were made of 4 layers except of the domes (iii)-(iv) consisted of 8 plies. The stacking sequences used for the shells which were tested were: $[0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ]$ - 4 plies and $[0_2^\circ, +45_2^\circ, -45_2^\circ, 0_2^\circ]$ - 8 plies. Of course, in practice the lay-up sequences may be produced in the circumferential directions of doubly-curved shells in an approximate manner only. The experimental and theoretical failure pressures of 12 FRP shells which were tested are given in Table 2. As it may be noticed the theoretical failure pressures are identified with the buckling ones since the bifurcation buckling is a dominating failure mode for the shells considered herein. The correlation of the experimental results with the theoretical predictions is reasonably satisfactory. In general, the theoretical predictions are lower than the test results. However, the experiments confirmed the theoretical predictions dealing with the influence of geometrical ratios on failure pressures. Discrepancies between theory and experiments can arise from assumptions used in the method of calculation and in the fabrication of the models. The

Table 1. Geometrical parameters of fabricated heads.

	Head	D [mm]	Geometrical ratios
I	Torispherical	272	$R/D=1.0, r/D=0.1$
II	Hemispherical	215	$R/D=0.5$
III	Torispherical	207	$R/D=0.6, r/D=0.35$
IV	Ellipsoidal	207	$a=D/2, b/a=0.8, L/D=0.0$
V	Ellipsoidal	207	$a=D/2, b/a=0.8, L/D=0.1$
VI	Ellipsoidal	207	$a=D/2, b/a=0.8, L/D=1.0$

Table 2. A comparison of the experimental and theoretical failure pressures.

	Material	Head number	D/(2t)	Experimental failure pressure p_{expt} [MPa]	Theoretical buckling pressure p_{th} [MPa]	p_{expt}/p_{th}
(i)	CFRP	I	84.47	1.31	1.36	0.96
(ii)	CFRP	I	84.47	1.29	1.36	0.95
(iii)	CFRP	I	42.235	5.03	5.46	0.92
(iv)	CFRP	I	42.235	5.21	5.46	0.95
(v)	GFRP	II	85.32	2.14	2.465	0.87
(vi)	GFRP	II	85.32	2.30	2.465	0.93
(vii)	GFRP	III	82.14	1.46	1.82	0.80
(viii)	GFRP	III	82.14	1.76	1.82	0.97
(ix)	GFRP	IV	82.14	1.93	2.115	0.91
(x)	GFRP	IV	82.14	1.89	2.115	0.89
(xi)	GFRP	V	82.14	1.51	1.79	0.84
(xii)	GFRP	VI	82.14	0.27	0.328	0.82

experimental failure shapes of the shells exhibited single cracks off the axis of symmetry - Fig.6. The forms of the failure patterns for the tested shells depend on the total height of the domes and their shapes.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The support from the KBN under the grant PB-232/T07/95/08 is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. A.Muc, Computational models and variational formulations for laminated composite structures. *Proc. ICCM/9* vol.3 (edt A. Miravete), Woodhead Publ., 86-94 (1993).
2. N.J.Pagano, Exact moduli of anisotropic laminates. *Composite Materials* Vol.2, 23-37 (1974).
3. A.Muc, Buckling, postbuckling and failure analysis of doubly-curved composite shells of revolution. *Proc. First European Conf. Num. Meth. in Engng.* (edt Ch.Hirsch), Elsevier, Amsterdam, 645-652 (1992).
4. A.Muc, J.Ryś, W.Latas, Limit load carrying capacity for spherical laminated shells under external pressure. *J.Composite Str.* **25**, 295-303 (1993).
5. A.Muc, Transverse shear effects in shape optimization of thinwalled laminated composite structures. *J.Composite Str.* (1995 in print).
6. A.Muc, Layout optimization of doubly-curved laminated composite shells of revolution. *Engng.Comp.* (submitted for publication).

Fig.1 The division of shell segment.

Fig.2 Variations of failure pressures.

Fig.3 The comparison with design codes.

Fig.4 The influence of the $2t^{head}/D$ ratio.

Fig.5 Optimal failure pressures.

Fig.6 Photograph of the model (i).